

NGS data analysis

Whole genome sequencing libraries for two GBS isolates (AC-13238-1, ERR3464558 and AC-13238-2, ERR3464559) were generated using Nextera DNA Library Preparation Kit (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA). The libraries were sequenced in an Illumina MiSeq system instrument using 150-cycles v2 paired-end cartridges. The raw reads of each isolate were assembled with the INNUca pipeline (<https://github.com/B-UMMI/INNUca>, version 4.2.0) using the default parameters for quality control with FastQC (<https://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>, version 0.11.8), quality filtering with Trimmomatic¹ (version 0.38), assembly with SPAdes² (version 3.13) and assembly polishing with Bowtie2³ (version 2.2.9) and Pilon⁴ (version 1.23).

Variant calling of each isolate was performed against the *de novo* assembly of the other isolate using Snippy (version 4.3.6; <https://github.com/tseemann/snippy/releases/tag/v4.3.6>), with default parameters, in order to determine genomic differences between both isolates.

The assemblies were sorted according to the complete ASM19605 genome (GCF_000196055.1) using Mauve (2015-02-13 snapshot)⁴. The sorted assembled genomes were annotated with Prokka⁵ (version 1.13.7).

The genomic comparison of AC-13238-1 and AC-13238-2 against the genomes of seven serotype Ia/CC23 isolates was obtained using the BLAST Ring Image Generator⁶ (BRIG, version 0.95, with *upper identity threshold 90%, lower identity threshold 70%* and BLAST options *-e-value 0.001*).

The core genome MLST (cgMLST) analysis was performed on the *de novo* assembled genomes, obtained from the INNUca pipeline, with the chewBBACA⁷ suite (version 2.0.17.1). The schema was obtained for the assembled genomes using the *Streptococcus agalactiae* training file for Prodigal⁸ provided with chewBBACA. The allele call for the wgMLST schema was conducted with default parameters and the cgMLST profile was extracted based on the loci present on 95% of isolates.

To establish the relationships between STs, the goeBURST algorithm implemented in the PHYLOViZ Online⁹ (<http://online2.phyloviz.net/index>) software was used.

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